

A STUDY ON $+\theta/-\theta$ INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES

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INTRODUCTION

Delamination of Composites exhibits a behavior that can often be described by the assumption of LEFM. G criterion proved to be powerful in Wang and other authors' study of laminates crack growth prediction. Considerable progress has been made in experimental and theoretical studies on G_c values for delamination of unidirectional composites by Rybicki, Keary, Donaldson and other investigators. But little work has been reported on G_c evaluation for $+\theta/-\theta$ interlaminar fracture because of the difficulties among which is that thermal residual stresses involved makes both theoretical and experimental studies even more complex. In this study, an approach is explored making it possible to evaluate mechanical and thermal parts of G_c separately.

THEORY AND CONDITIONS OF THE METHOD

For a general composite laminate subjected to both mechanical and thermal loading, the available strain energy release rate is a function of mechanical strain, temperature drop ΔT and crack length a , and can be expressed as

$$G = (\sqrt{G_m} + \sqrt{G_T})^2$$

where G_m is the energy release rate when mechanical load is applied exclusively and, similarly, G_T is that of pure thermal loading.

In the case of unidirectional composites, no thermal Component G_T is involved and material property G_c can be examined by mechanical loading tests without concerning thermal problems. But in general cases, the strain energy includes three parts:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \sigma_m \epsilon_m dv + \frac{1}{2} \int_V \sigma_T \epsilon_T dv + \frac{1}{2} \int_V (\sigma_m \epsilon_T + \sigma_T \epsilon_m) dv$$

or

$$U = U_m + U_T + U_{mT}$$

To determine G_m experimentally, it is necessary to make sure that, during the loading and deforming of the specimen, U_{mT} remains zero as it can not yet be evaluated.

Applying beam and lamination theories to DCB specimens yields that if each single beam is a symmetric laminate and is subjected to pure bending, the term

$$U_{mT} = \int_V \sigma_m \epsilon_T dv \quad \text{or} \quad \int_V \sigma_T \epsilon_m dv$$

vanishes because thermal stress on the cross section is symmetrically distributed with respect to the neutral plane whereas mechanical strain is antisymmetric. Then, if the stacking sequence and the test are properly designed to meet above conditions, DCB specimens can still be used to determine G_m part of G_c .

Pure thermal part G_T can be expressed as

$$G_T = C_T \cdot (\Delta T)^2 \cdot t$$

where C_T for each specimen group was computed on VAX-11/785 by a 3-D finite element analysis program employing Irwin crack closure and double nodes techniques for delamination simulation, for no direct test method is available.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

T300/648 prepregs were used to make DCB specimens (13mm x 240mm) with a pre-made through width mid-plane delamination nearly 40mm long at one end where later a pair of aluminum loading adherends were placed. Two stacking sequences were chosen, namely $[+\theta_6/-\theta_6]$ and $[+\theta/-\theta]_7$ ($\theta=0, 7.5^\circ, 15^\circ, 22.5^\circ$ and 30°). After each measuring of crack length a_i , the constant displacement test machine started to load from zero and the i -th $P-\Delta$ curve was recorded till crack advanced, then the machine was stopped and ready for measuring the next crack length. The procedure was repeated resulting in about 20 crack extensions per specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL DATA REDUCTION

Three different calibration procedures were programed and computer performed:

1. Based upon energy analysis and beam theory, G_m of the specimen can be determined as

$$G_1 = F_1 \cdot F_2 \cdot \frac{3}{2} \frac{P\Delta}{Ba}$$

where F_1 is proposed by Williams which amends only the distance a to \bar{x} in bending moment evaluation. The new correction factor

$$F_2 = 1 - h \sqrt{\frac{3\delta}{a^3} \sin\alpha}$$

is deduced and suggested in this study if the height of end tabs is not negligible which is often the case.

2. Using polynomial fitting of experimentally measured compliance and equation of LEF

$$G_1 = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da}$$

3. For elastic behavior, G_1 is equivalent to J_1 and may be defined as

$$J_1 = \left. \frac{-1}{B} \frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \right|_{\Delta = \text{const.}}$$

suggesting a direct approach for calculating J_1 from recorded $P-\Delta$ curves. [Landes and Begley, Keary]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results for $[+\theta_6/-\theta_6]$ are given below and the trend seems to be obvious. When θ increases from 0 to 30° , the total value of G_c of mixed mode fracture increases and so does the ratio $(G_{11}+G_{111})/G_1$ while G_1 part decreases.

For $[+\theta/-\theta]_7$ type, experimentally obtained G_m values are even higher than total G_c of corresponding $[+\theta_6/-\theta_6]$ specimens for larger θ 's. The reason is that more fracture surfaces were formed.

FRACTOGRAPHY

Typical fracture surfaces of each specimen group were gold-coated for SEM examination. The images were taken and phenomena summarized that supplies rich information helpful in understanding the physics of $+\theta/-\theta$ delamination and explaining experimental data.

CONCLUSIONS

Some important information of $+\theta/-\theta$ interlaminar fracture and fracture toughness was obtained. The relative trend should be of general meaning. The study explored an approach to evaluate $+\theta/-\theta$ interlaminar G_c by properly designed DCB experiments for G_m examination combined with numerical computation of G_T . But the investigator should be aware of the theory basis and the limitation when using DCB tests to non-unidirectional composites. By changing stacking sequences of the specimens, different ratio of $G_1:G_{11}:G_{111}$ can be achieved, and the whole picture of G_c will be seen for a specific angle θ .

Table 1. Experimental G_m by different calibration schemes (J/M^2)

$\theta(^{\circ})$	0	7.5	15	22.5	30
scheme 1	110.6	83.3	99.0	69.0	55.7
scheme 2	106.2	83.4	103.3	67.1	51.9
scheme 3	105.3	83.6	92.8	69.5	52.0

Table 2. Results (J/M^2)

$\theta(^{\circ})$	0	7.5	15	22.5	30
G_1	107.4	92.2	120.0	96.1	82.1
G_{11}		0.4	2.6	8.2	17.5
G_{111}		2.4	11.8	27.6	41.6
G_c	107.4	95.0	134.4	131.9	141.2

Fig.1 Specimen

Fig.2 0/0 and +30/-30 fracture surfaces